

1. May the soil of my land grow green.

(ACAAGTACAGCTAGCGTCTAAGCTGATGTCTGATCAGCTGTGCTAGCACAGACAGCATCACTCTCTACAGCGTCCACTGTATGA
GCGTCCACCTACTACTC)

2. May Allah make this land prosperous.

(ACAAGTACAGCACTATCATCACTCGTAGCACAACTTCGCTAAGCTAGCGTCTGTGAAGCATCACTCTCTACAGCGAG
CACTGTTGAGAGCTACACTGTGATTGA)

3. You are the sign of strength my magnificent land.

(GACTGTGATAGCACTCACCTAAGCTAGCGTCTAAGCTGACTGGTCTCAGCTGTGCTAGCTGATAGCACCTACTCGTCT
AGCGTAGCACAGACAGCACAACTGTCTCTGGCTCTGTCACTACTCTAGAGCATCACTCTCTAC)

=====
4. The center of my hopes, may you become prosperous.

(TAGCGTCTAAGCTCACTACTCTAGCTACACAGCTGTGCTAGCACAGACAGCCGTTGTGAGCTATGAAGCACAAGTAC
AGCGACTGTGATAGCCATCTATCATGTACACTAAGCGAGCACTGTTGAGAGCTACACTGTGATTGA)

=====
5. The network of my land.

(TAGCGTCTAAGCCTCCTATAGATGTGCTACTCGAGCTGTGCTAGCACAGACAGCATCACTCTCTAC)

=====
6. The power of brotherhood.

(TAGCGTCTAAGCGAGTGTATGCTACACAGCTGTGCTAGCCATCACTGTTAGCGTCTACACCGTTGTTGTTAC)

=====
7. Oh my nation, my country, my empire.

(TGTCGTAGCACAGACAGCCTCACTTAGCTGTGTCTCAGCACAGACAGCTCATGTGATCTCTAGCACGACAGCACAGAC
AGCCTAACAGAGCTGCACCTA)

=====
8. May you last for eternity and may you endure your long destination.

(AGGACGACAAGTACAGCGACTGTGATAGCATCACTTGATAGAGCGCTTGTCACAGCCTATAGCTACACCTCCTGTAG
GACAGCACTCTCTACAGCACAAGTACAGCGACTGTGATAGCCTACTCTACGATCACCTAAGCGACTGTGATCACAGC
AGCATCTGTCTCGTCAGCTACCTATGATAGCTGCTCACTTAGCTGTGTCTC)

=====

9. may you endure your long destination.

(ACAACTGACAGCGACTGTGATAGCCTACTCTACGATCACCTAAGCGACTGTGATCACAGCATCTGTCTCGTCAGCTAC
CTATGATAGCTGCTCACTTAGCTGTGTCTC)

10. Your star and crescent flag.

(GACTGTGATCACAGCTGATAGACTCACAGCACTCTCTACAGCTCACACCTATGATCACTACTCTAGAGCGCTATCACTG
TC)

=====

11. You are the leader of development and perfection.

(AGCGACTGTGATAGCACTCACCTAAGCTAGCGTCTAAGCATCCTAACTTACCTACACAGCTGTGCTAGCTACCTAGTAC
TAATCTGTGAGACACTACTCTAGAGCACTCTCTACAGCGAGCTACACGCTCTATCATAGCTGTGTCTC)

=====

12. A representative of our glorious history! my life.

(AGCACTAGCCACCTAGAGCACCTATGACTACTCTAGACTTAGCTGGTACTAAGCTGTGCTAGCTGTGATCACAGCGTC
ATCTGTCACCTGTGTGATTGAAGCCGTCTGTGATAGTGTACAGACAGCACAGACAGCATCCTGGCTCTA)

13. The glorious.

AGCTAGCGTCTAAGCGTCATCTGTCACCTGTGTGATTGA
